

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Gastric Aspirate Cytology for Neonatal Sepsis Screening in Very Low Birth Weight Infants

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Abstract:

Introduction: Neonatal sepsis is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in very low birth weight (VLBW) infants, necessitating rapid and accurate diagnostic methods. Gastric aspirate cytology has been revisited as a potential early screening tool due to its non-invasiveness and rapid turnaround.

Methodology: This prospective, observational, multicentric study involved 95 VLBW infants assessed for neonatal sepsis from September 2015 to August 2016. Gastric aspirates were collected within six hours of birth and analyzed for bacterial presence and cellularity, compared against gold-standard blood cultures and clinical outcomes.

Results: Gastric aspirate cytology demonstrated a sensitivity of 70% and a specificity of 85%. Infants with positive cytology results were more likely to require prolonged hospitalization and mechanical ventilation. Statistical analysis highlighted significant correlations between cytological findings and adverse clinical outcomes, underscoring the potential clinical utility of this method.

Conclusion: While gastric aspirate cytology cannot replace blood cultures due to lower sensitivity, its high specificity suggests it can serve as an effective adjunct tool for early sepsis screening in VLBW infants. This method may guide early treatment decisions, potentially improving outcomes in this high-risk group.

Recommendation: Future research should aim to standardize gastric aspirate cytology techniques and explore integration with other diagnostic approaches to enhance sensitivity and overall clinical value. Adopting this method in combination with current diagnostic standards could better stratify risk and tailor early interventions in neonatal care settings.

Keywords: Neonatal Sepsis, Very Low Birth Weight Infants, Gastric Aspirate Cytology, Diagnostic Screening, Clinical Outcomes.

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Introduction

Neonatal sepsis is a critical concern in neonatology due to its high morbidity and mortality rates, especially in very low birth weight (VLBW) infants [1]. VLBW infants, those born weighing less than 1500 grams, are particularly susceptible to infections because of their immature immune systems and the higher likelihood of invasive procedures during their intensive care [2]. Prompt and accurate diagnosis of sepsis is paramount to initiating timely treatment and improving survival rates. However, the traditional methods for diagnosing neonatal sepsis, primarily reliant on clinical signs and laboratory tests like blood

cultures, pose significant challenges [3,4]. Blood cultures, though definitive, are time-consuming and may yield false negatives due to the small volumes of blood that can be safely drawn from these infants. Additionally, the clinical signs of sepsis in neonates are often nonspecific, leading to diagnostic uncertainty and potential delays in treatment [5,6].

In this context, there is a pressing need for alternative diagnostic approaches that are both rapid and reliable. Gastric aspirate cytology has been investigated as a potential screening tool in this regard. This method involves analyzing the

cellular components of gastric aspirates—fluid retrieved from the stomach—which can contain swallowed amniotic fluid and potential pathogens. The presence of certain pathogens or abnormal cellular patterns in the gastric aspirate might suggest an infection, providing a non-invasive and immediate indicator of sepsis [7,8].

Historically, the use of gastric aspirate cytology in neonatal sepsis has been limited, partly due to its variable sensitivity and specificity in past studies. Moreover, the technique has not been standardized, which has resulted in inconsistent application and varying results across different neonatal units. Despite these challenges, the potential for gastric aspirate cytology to provide rapid diagnostic insights—particularly in a population as vulnerable as VLBW infants—warrants a thorough reevaluation [9,10].

This study aims to systematically reassess the effectiveness and reliability of gastric aspirate cytology as a screening tool for early-onset neonatal sepsis in VLBW infants. We intend to explore its potential benefits and limitations through a detailed analysis of gastric aspirate samples, comparing its diagnostic performance with traditional methods. This could potentially lead to quicker diagnosis and treatment, significantly affecting the clinical outcomes for these high-risk neonates.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective, observational, multicentric study conducted to evaluate the efficacy of gastric aspirate cytology as a screening tool for neonatal sepsis in very low birth weight (VLBW) infants.

Study Setting: The research was carried out across neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) at DMCH, Darbhanga & GMC, Bettiha, Bihar hospitals. The study spanned from September 2015 to August 2016, encompassing a broad range of medical practices and patient demographics, which strengthens the generalizability of the findings.

Participants: A total of 95 VLBW infants were enrolled in this study. The infants were admitted to the NICUs during the study period and required a clinical evaluation for suspected sepsis based on either clinical symptoms or risk factors.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- Infants with a birth weight of less than 1500 grams.
- Infants admitted to the NICU within the first 72 hours of life.

Exclusion criteria:

- Infants with major congenital anomalies.

- Infants whose parents or guardians did not consent to participate in the study.

Bias: To minimize potential sources of bias, the study utilized a blinded analysis where the laboratory technicians analyzing the gastric aspirates were not aware of the infants' clinical status. Furthermore, data collection was standardized across all participating centers to ensure consistency in the interpretation of results.

Data Collection and Analysis: Gastric aspirates were collected within the first six hours of life, before the initiation of any antibiotic therapy. The aspirates were analyzed for the presence of bacteria and abnormal cell counts, which were then correlated with blood culture results and clinical outcomes. Data on clinical signs, laboratory markers, and treatments were also collected to comprehensively assess the utility of gastric aspirate cytology as a diagnostic tool.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of gastric aspirate cytology were calculated and compared with those of blood cultures. Logistic regression analysis was used to control for potential confounders. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations: The study was approved by the ethical review boards. Informed consent was obtained from the parents or guardians of all participating infants. All study procedures were conducted by the ethical standards of the responsible committee on human experimentation and with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, as revised in 2000.

Results

The study's findings demonstrate the potential utility of gastric aspirate cytology as a screening tool for neonatal sepsis in very low birth weight (VLBW) infants. The results revealed a sensitivity of 70% and a specificity of 85% for gastric aspirate cytology when compared to gold-standard blood cultures. The analysis showed that infants with a positive gastric aspirate cytology result were more likely to require extended hospitalization and mechanical ventilation, underscoring the clinical relevance of the test. Statistical analysis confirmed that gastric aspirate cytology could serve as an early indicator of sepsis, potentially guiding more prompt and targeted interventions. Additionally, the use of logistic regression highlighted significant associations between positive cytology results and adverse clinical outcomes, emphasizing the

importance of early and accurate sepsis detection in this vulnerable population.

Overall, this study suggests that while gastric aspirate cytology does not replace blood cultures, it could be considered a useful adjunctive tool,

especially for early screening in settings where immediate blood culture results are not feasible. This could lead to quicker therapeutic interventions, potentially improving clinical outcomes in VLBW infants suspected of sepsis.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Total Participants (n=95)
Age at Sampling (hours)	< 6 hours
Gender (% Male)	52%
Birth Weight (grams)	1200±300
Gestational Age (weeks)	28±3
Premature Rupture of Membranes (% cases)	30%
Maternal Infection (% cases)	25%

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants: This table summarizes the baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of the 95 participating VLBW infants. Variables include age at sampling, gender, birth weight, gestational age, and the presence of risk factors for sepsis such as premature rupture of membranes and maternal infections.

Table 2: Diagnostic Performance of Gastric Aspirate Cytology

Metric	Gastric Aspirate Cytology	Blood Cultures
Sensitivity	70%	90%
Specificity	85%	95%
Positive Predictive Value	75%	88%
Negative Predictive Value	82%	90%

Table 2: Diagnostic Performance of Gastric Aspirate Cytology: Table 2 details the diagnostic performance of gastric aspirate cytology, including sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV). These metrics are compared alongside those for blood cultures, providing a direct assessment of the effectiveness of gastric aspirate cytology in diagnosing neonatal sepsis.

Table 3: Correlation between Gastric Aspirate Findings and Clinical Outcomes

Outcome	Positive Gastric Aspirate	Negative Gastric Aspirate
Duration of Hospital Stay (days)	18±5	12±3
Need for Mechanical Ventilation (% cases)	40%	20%
Mortality Rate (%)	15%	5%

Table 3: Correlation between Gastric Aspirate Findings and Clinical Outcomes: This table correlates the findings from gastric aspirate cytology with clinical outcomes such as duration of hospital stay, need for mechanical ventilation, and mortality rates. It provides insight into how early diagnostic information might influence clinical decision-making and outcomes in VLBW infants.

Discussion

The study demonstrated that gastric aspirate cytology has a sensitivity of 70% and a specificity of 85% for detecting neonatal sepsis in very low birth weight (VLBW) infants. Additionally, the presence of positive cytology findings correlated with longer hospital stays and increased requirements for mechanical ventilation. The sensitivity and specificity rates suggest that while gastric aspirate cytology is not sufficiently robust on its own to replace blood cultures, it does hold potential as an adjunct screening tool. The ability of gastric aspirate cytology to identify sepsis earlier than traditional blood cultures could be particularly

advantageous in clinical settings where rapid intervention is crucial. The associations found between positive cytology results and more severe clinical outcomes emphasize the potential clinical relevance of the test in managing VLBW infants.

Previous studies have reported varying results for the sensitivity and specificity of gastric aspirate cytology, with some studies achieving higher sensitivity but generally lower specificity. For instance, research by O'Connor et al. (2012) [11] reported higher sensitivity rates of around 80%, but a significantly lower specificity of approximately 60%. The variation in performance metrics across studies can largely be attributed to differences in sample collection techniques, cytological methods, and the timing of sample collection relative to birth and antibiotic administration [12,13].

The relatively high specificity observed in this study suggests that a positive result from gastric aspirate cytology is a strong indicator of sepsis, which could help clinicians initiate treatment more confidently [14]. However, the lower sensitivity

indicates a risk of false negatives, where some cases of sepsis may not be detected by cytology alone. This limitation underscores the importance of combining cytology with other diagnostic indicators, such as clinical signs or molecular diagnostics, to enhance overall detection rates [15,16].

Furthermore, the correlation between positive cytological findings and adverse outcomes highlights the potential for this method to identify infants at higher risk of complications, guiding more intensive monitoring and treatment. This aspect of gastric aspirate cytology could be particularly beneficial in resource-limited settings where rapid lab diagnostics like PCR are unavailable or impractical [17].

Conclusion

This study highlights the potential of gastric aspirate cytology as a supportive screening tool for early detection of neonatal sepsis in very low birth weight infants, demonstrating a specificity of 85% and sensitivity of 70%. Although it cannot replace the gold standard blood cultures due to its lower sensitivity, its high specificity indicates that it could be particularly useful in guiding early treatment decisions in clinical settings. The positive correlation between abnormal cytological findings and severe clinical outcomes underscores its value in identifying infants at risk for adverse effects, suggesting that when used in conjunction with other diagnostic methods, gastric aspirate cytology could enhance the overall strategy for managing sepsis in this vulnerable population. Future research should focus on standardizing the technique and exploring integrative diagnostic approaches to improve its diagnostic accuracy and clinical applicability.

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